

ISic3615

I.Sicily inscription 3615

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

natural rock

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)**Place of origin (modern)**

Castelluccio

Provenance

'versante meridionale della Cava della Signora, in uno spazioso ambiente ipogeico aperto a Nord'

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Castelluccio, in situ

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 645688

Bibliography

1923-. Supplementum epigraphicum graecum. *Supplementum epigraphicum graecum*. At 58.1049.2

undefined, undefined, undefined, undefined, undefined, undefined 1876-.

Notizie degli scavi di antichità. *Notizie degli scavi di antichità*. At 354

Rizzone, V.G. 2008. Vecchie e nuove, vere e presunte iscrizioni tardo-antiche della campagna Netina. *Nea Rhome*. 5: 17-26. At 18 fig.2

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